

THE MAIN THREE TYPES OF LEARNING STYLES AND UTILIZING THEM IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT: This article aims to give a bunch of instructions about types of learners and learning styles. Article is provided with some important details and examples. According to preference of learners, learning divided into three main groups namely auditory learning, visual learning and kinesthetic or tactile learning groups. This article can help students and novices to learn these types of learning much deeper and they may improve their knowledge with the help of it. In addition to, they can identify by themselves which learning style is suitable for them and what aspects are handy for them to increase their skills very easily and fast.

Key words: learning styles, auditory learner, visual learner, kinesthetic/tactile learner, education.

INTRODUCTION

What is learning language ?

Language learning is an active process that begins at birth and continues throughout life. Students learn language as they use it to communicate their thoughts, feelings, and experiences, establish relationships with family members and friends, and strive to make sense and order of their world.

While you are learning a foreign language or a second language you use one of learning styles or methods. It is so important to follow learning styles to learn another language. The process of learning second language is called interlanguage.

What is interlanguage?

Interlanguage is a developing system with its interim structure, rather than an imperfect imitation of the TL. It is a systematic, predictable but also dynamic, continually evolving as learners receive more input and revise their hypothesis about the Teaching Language.

TYPES OF LEARNING STYLES

According to the preferences of learners, learning divided three most important types that Auditory learning, Visual learning, Kinesthetic or Tactile learning.

Mostly, people use the auditory learning style who prefer to learn something by listening or hearing voices or tracks.

AUDITORY learning style

You understand and remember things you have heard. You store information by the way it sounds, and you have an easier time understanding spoken instructions than written ones. During the lessons, especially, in lectures students who are auditory learners can get them entirely by hearing than writing something or watching presentation. Auditory imagery may include: Enjoyable sounds, such as: beautiful music, birdsong, and the voices of a chorus. Noises, such as: the bang of a gun, the sound of a broom moving across the floor, and the sound of broken glass shattering on the floor.

In this learning type, students can develop their skill by training more listening exercises. In this case, songs, tracks and records aid them to learn better. In primary school children who are natural auditory learners prefer to learn through speaking, listening and audio-based educational resources such as music and podcasts.

Characteristics

Auditory learning style – this means you learn by hearing and listening. Acquire knowledge by reading aloud • Hum and/or talk to yourself • Make comments like: “I hear you clearly.” “I want you to listen.” “This sounds good.”

Furthermore, They enjoy listening but cannot wait to get a chance to talk. They tend toward long and repetitive descriptions. They like hearing themselves and others talk. They tend to remember names but forget faces and are easily distracted by sounds.

There are some activities to improve auditory learners’ skills, however they are different according to learners age such as:

Activities for Auditory Learners :

Read homework directions out loud

Record facts on video and then replay it. A mobile phone or tablet works well for this strategy.

Sing facts to a tune

Write a song when memorizing facts or spelling words

Teach to other students or even to stuffed animals

Practice in front of a mirror

Try a whisper phone

Listen to books on tape using headphones

Rhyme facts

Spell words out loud in different pitches and tones

Use noise eliminating headphones in the classroom or during tests

Find a quiet space for homework

Turn off distractions. Consider televisions, phones, or even fans

Use mnemonic devices to memorize facts

Listen to audiobooks

Use oral reports for classroom projects

Allow students to record portions of homework or projects onto devices

Make flashcards and read them out loud

During classroom lessons, clap or speak louder during important parts

Speak in syllables

Which activities do you use to improve your skill regularly?

VISUAL learning style

Visual. If you are a visual learner, you learn by reading or seeing pictures. You understand and remember things by sight. You can picture what you are learning in your head, and you learn best by using methods that are primarily visual. You like to see what you are learning. They prefer looking at things to absorb information rather than listening to it (auditory) or using their hands (kinesthetic). For example, a visual learner would learn to fix a car better if they watch an instructional video rather than listening to an expert explain the process. Visual learning also helps students to develop visual thinking, which is a learning style whereby the learner comes better to understand and retain information better by associating ideas, words and concepts with images.

Exceptionally, some individuals are talented naturally who are weak to hear by their ears that they try to use their visual option as possible as they can. The deaf are explained by illustrations, pictures and videos namely they can understand by these items rather than listening and touching. In education, teachers use a great deal of useful tools such as colourful stickers, maps, presentations, draws and others to improve students' skills and knowledge.

And there are numerous lucrative puppets to provide and to develop visual learning style. For instance:

Color-Code

Visual learners should invest in a good pack of highlighters of many colors and use the various colors to 'code' information they are learning. For example, related topics can be assigned a specific color in their notes. Colored index cards are also a good tool for visual learners, and colored pens will help keep their attention when taking notes during class.

Draw

They can also draw things they are visualizing. When visual learners 'see' something that helps them to better understand something, they should take a few moments to jot down the image in their mind. This will help them to process what it is they are visualizing

Create Mind Maps

They can create mind maps. A mind map is a tool visual learners can create to help them visually organize information and is much like a visual outline. These maps center around one topic and include branches for each related main idea. Mind maps can include keywords, examples, images, and more. Many software companies offer free tools for creating online mind maps.

Utilizing graphic organizers

Charts and tables are great ways for visual learners to organize information into a visual format that is easy to comprehend.

Below list of examples of activities to develop visual learning style:

Building puzzles.

Playing with construction toys.

Playing memory games.

Drawing, painting, cutting, pasting, folding.

Making patterns (with beads, pegs, etc.)

Playing with and tracing shapes.

Sorting objects.

Matching colours.

KINESTHETIC/TACTILE learning styles

Kinaesthetic learning happens when we have a hands-on experience. An example of a kinaesthetic learning experience is when a child learns to use a swing or to ride a bike. They can read instructions or listen to instructions, but deep learning occurs via the process of doing. They try things out, touch, feel and manipulate objects. Body tension is a good indication of their emotions. They gesture when speaking, are poor listeners, stand very close when speaking or listening, and quickly lose interest in long discourse.

Tactile learners, they prefer to physically act out events or use all of their senses while learning. These types of learners are easy to find, as they likely have a difficult time sitting still and might need frequent breaks during heavy studying periods.

This learning style encourages physical activity, bolsters cognitive, social, and emotional development, enhances the brain's capacity to retain information, and develops not just one's individual capacities and strengths, but also one's self-confidence in those capacities.

Kinesthetic learning strategies

- Work standing up. ...
- Use small movements to help focus. ...
- Build exercise into your workday. ...
- Use a highlighter and flashcards. ...
- Approach topics creatively. ...
- Use tension and relaxation. ...
- Use role-play. ...
- Consider simulations.

Totally, kinesthetic and tactile learning styles are similar but there is difference between them. Tactile perception refers to the sense of touch, while kinesthetic perception deals with the sense of body movements and muscle feelings. Tactile learners like to write things down or take notes when learning. They also like to doodle and draw. They tend to enjoy reading books, writing stories, and illustrating what they have learned. Kinesthetic learners learn best by doing.

Together, they provide information about object qualities, bodily movements, and their interrelationships. They thus constitute the basic rubric of perceptual-motor learning.

Chalfant and Scheffelin observed that the child having problems in haptic processing has difficulties dealing with information, on the one hand, relating to geometry, texture, pressure, pain or temperature, and, on the other, about the body itself when in motion or in static position. In general, the problems noted in the learning disabled in the area of haptic perception fall in the following components:

Tactile discrimination. This refers to the ability to feel the differences between objects. The child with a difficulty in this area is unable to recognize differences in objects through touch alone. Thus, differences in texture, temperature, and shapes of hidden objects elude the child.

Body image. This refers to the awareness of one's own body and the relation of body parts to each other. The child who has a problem in this area not only lacks awareness of body parts in relation to each other, but also is unable to identify them. Finger agnosia, an inability to tell fingers apart or touch when blindfolded, is a frequently mentioned problem.

Kinesthetic Activities for English language learners:

Using gestures to represent key vocabulary words.

Making puppets and presenting puppet shows.

Designing graphics and creating artwork to represent story concepts.

Playing charades.

Learning strategies of tactile learners

- Work with quiet music in the background.
- Take regular short breaks.
- Close your eyes and trek words or images with your finger.
- Make games, puzzles out of what you are learning.
- Do roleplays, performances or demonstrations of the information.
- Read notes while pacing

CONCLUSION

In this article I displayed three types of learning styles that auditory style, visual style and kinesthetic/tactile learning styles. They are divided into these groups on the authority of students' preferably learning way. When students use only one type of learning style they improve their preferred learning type better and better.

Above I described three types of styles entirely and I hope novices can learn items with the help of this inputs. Being aware of the types of learning is so necessary and children in primary and secondary schools and also students in higher education can use this inputs when they need.

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